

DEALING WITH PROBLEMS RELATED TO STUDENT ENGAGEMENT IN TEACHING EFL

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ANNOTATION

A successful EFL class requires strong student engagement, which is a crucial interactional and pedagogical responsibility. Teachers could face complications during lessons, which prompts them to investigate at ways to solve issues with classroom involvement. In order for solutions, data were collected from five EFL teachers who work at schools using interview questions. The interview questions incorporated a number of topics, including motivation, resources, teaching and learning, and class management practices.

Keywords: *Student engagement, English as a first language (EFL), classroom, strategies.*

1. Introduction

The term "student engagement" refers how involved, interested, and passionate the students are to participate in the class. One way to think of student engagement is as the bonding agent that binds all the components of learning and development together. It has been demonstrated that student engagement has important effects on learners in addition to making teaching itself more enjoyable, interesting, and rewarding. Students are more likely to succeed academically, feel more connected to

their school, and have better social-emotional well-being when they exhibit high levels of behavioral, emotional, and cognitive engagement. Conversely, low student engagement has been linked to a number of unfavorable outcomes, including substance use, violence, delinquency, and school dropout. While these concerning results usually manifest in adolescence, low involvement in elementary and middle school can put students on a downward spiral. Promoting student engagement at all grade levels is therefore essential.

2. Literature review

One of the most significant pedagogical and interactive tasks that students can demonstrate their involvement in is through classroom participation. In this study, "classroom participation" refers to the amount of student involvement in classroom discussions and student-teacher conversation. In this regard, a number of professionals and experts in the field of teaching English have emphasized the significance of oral engagement by students in the classroom. According to Jackson (2002), students might construct and shape their identities as classroom participants in the environment that their participation in the classroom offers. As a result, involvement in language classes is crucial since it makes the teaching and learning process more engaging. When all the students can hear is the professor speaking, it can be challenging to keep their attention. Hearing an alternative viewpoint from someone other than the instructor is beneficial.

One of the problems that many teachers have is low student involvement. The topic of student participation in the classroom has been the subject of numerous research. This problem continues for a number of reasons. The views of educators and the classroom atmosphere may play a big role in students' disengagement from the learning process (Denessen, 2015). The same study also found that when teachers were passionate about the subjects they were teaching, students felt more positively about the subjects as well. It was established that teacher attitudes had a direct impact on students' attitudes. Wang (2020), who demonstrated that classroom engagement and

student achievement are positively connected with classroom quality, support the notion that students' perceptions of their teachers correspond with involvement. The teacher's emotional support, the instructional support system, and the classroom organisation all contributed to the quality of the classroom. It has also been demonstrated that other teaching strategies, such as memorising information, repetitious tasks, and textbook-based labour, negatively affect student involvement (Lyons, 2006). Moreover, instructors might not possess the necessary knowledge or expertise to provide students with the academic and emotional support they need to stay engaged (Dar, 2015). If, as research indicates, student engagement is positively correlated with achievement, then low student engagement poses a serious challenge (Faris, 2008; Vaughn & Winner, 2000; Maltese & Tai, 2010). The US ranked just 38th out of 71 countries in maths and 24th in science according to a 2015 assessment conducted by the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), which compared the US to various other nations. Additionally, the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) revealed that, for the first time since 1990, the average math scores of fourth and eighth graders decreased in 2015 (United Nations, 2014).

3. Methodology

The aim of this article is analyzing problems teachers might face with student engagement while teaching EFL classroom. For doing this, interview method is used and five teachers are selected and participated.

Participants.

N	Participants	Work place	Experience	What classes they teach	Level of the teacher
1.	Latipova Tursunoy	9th Fergana region	10 years	4th, 9th, 10th, 11th	C1
2.	Turdimatova Mahfuza	9th Fergana region	15 years	2nd, 5th, 6th, 11th	B2

3.	A'zamova Gulshoda	9th Fergana region	1 year	4th, 8th, 9th, 10th, 11th	C1
4.	Marufova Sarvinoz	29th Fergana region	2 years	1st, 2nd, 9th	C1
5.	O'ktamova Asila	29th Fergana region	2years	1st, 2nd, 9th	C1

Research method: Interview. An interview is a conversation for gathering information. A research interview involves an interviewer, who coordinates the process of the conversation and asks questions, and an interviewee, who responds to those questions.

When: 15th of October

Where: At school number 9, at university

How: Face-to-face

Data collecting tool: Interview.

Interview questions:

1. How do you engage all students when you are supposed to teach whole class?
2. How do you (or would you) punish 1st and 2nd grade students who are misbehaving or not paying attention to the lesson?
3. How do you deal with students who keep constantly talking?

4. Data analysis and discussion

Each of the interviewees I interacted with had a different response for the first question, providing various solutions for this problem. While T.M. stated it would be very helpful to start a class with a wonderful beginning so students keep their attention till the end of the lesson, L.T. and A.G. advised using more active games to keep students involved in the class. According to O'A., when a lesson is connected to something a student is interested in, they will participate in it more, hence teachers

should be aware of their students' interests. While L.T. suggests using a "magic box" to get kids' attention in elementary school, higher level pupils may find the lesson more engaging if they are given certain challenges to answer on their own.

Nearly every interviewee expressed the same opinion in response to the second question: young learners should never be punished. T.L. recommended that the students who actively participate in the class should be rewarded, so this action encourages the disobedient or passive kids to try to participate in order to receive the prize. T.M. made really intriguing point that, if you teach kids in the proper way, they would never resist learning. Since most young students learn best by kinesthetic, tactile, or visual ways, instructional strategies should be selected with these learning styles in mind. A.G. and S.M. recommended that teachers implement punishment cards or assign extra work or assignments, including memorization of new vocabulary or tongue twisters, to pupils who misbehave.

Regarding the third question, participants offered varying perspectives. L.T. responded that students who are chatty all the time should be engaged in extra activities. A teacher should give them more challenging tasks to keep them busy. T.M. stated that when working with these kinds of students, teachers should concentrate on speaking. They ought to be assigned more speaking-related tasks. A.G. recommended letting them speak first, and then the teacher could offer her own thoughts after students had finished. O'.A. and M.S. offered that extra activities can be used as a form of discipline for students who disrupt other students and make noise.

5. Conclusion

The results of this study indicate that one of the most common issues teachers might encounter in the classroom is low student engagement. Therefore, in order to conduct a lesson that is effective, a teacher is required to be able to control the classroom and get students' attention.

As students become easily disinterested in the same approach or atmosphere, there must always be something new to keep them engaged in the lesson. In particular, EFL

teachers ought to be imaginative in order to make each lesson engaging and unique. It's not always appropriate to punish students for not participating in the lesson, particularly when they are younger students. To engage every student, educators must come up with diverse exercises or apply a range of teaching strategies.

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